

ICN With DHT Support in Mobile Networks

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Abstract—Information-Centric Network (ICN) architectures, such as Named Data Networking (NDN), can improve content delivery on the Internet by deploying in-network caching techniques. Replacing the entire established Internet with a novel architecture is a non-trivial task, which is why this work develops a layered network architecture consisting of several smaller NDN-based mobile networks (resp., domains), interconnected using a Distributed Hash Table (DHT)-based network running as an overlay on top of existing Internet infrastructures. Using simulations, we model real-world network characteristics to evaluate the proposed architecture’s performance successfully.

I. INTRODUCTION

Contrary to the host-centricity of the Internet Protocol (IP), Information Centric Networks (ICN) stand as a novel paradigm focusing on the transported information itself. ICN addresses data directly. Therefore, packets hold a name describing the contained data instead of source and destination addresses. Several architectures implemented the ICN paradigm in recent years as “future technologies” to replace the traditional IP-based Internet [7], [12]. However, it is still debatable, whether ICNs are an optimal choice to replace the established IP-based ecosystem globally.

This work specifies, implements, and evaluates a novel network architecture for multi-domain ICN-based content delivery. The ICN is enhanced with a Distributed Hash Table (DHT)-based Peer-to-Peer (P2P) network to be used on an inter-domain level, running an overlay network on top of traditional IP-based Internet infrastructures. This demonstrates benefits compared to particular configurations of ICNs.

This work is organized in the following fashion. The following Section II presents related work. In Section III, the proposed architecture is described. In Section IV, the evaluation strategies and parameters are provided. The results from conducting several simulations are presented in Section V. Finally, Section VI summarizes the contributions of this work.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Named-Data Networking

Moving away from the classical host-based Internet paradigm, ICN is information-centric. Hosts in an ICN network request and deliver data according to names, instead of host addresses. Named Data Networking (NDN) [1], [12] is likely the most prominent implementation part of the ICN architecture family. Communication-wise, NDN operates by

exchanging the following two message types. (i) Interest packets hold an identifier (a name) and are used to inform the network about the demand to retrieve some named data item. (ii) Data packets carry the name and content of requested data items back to the information requester. NDN features three types of nodes, *i.e.*, content producers, content consumers, and intermediate forwarding routers. Content consumer nodes request data items by issuing interest packets, while intermediate nodes forward interest and data items. The interest message is forwarded to producers to inform them about the requested content. The corresponding data reply goes from producers to consumers, carrying the requested content. One of the most critical system parts of NDN is the NDN Forwarder, which resides in every node. The NDN Forwarder checks whether the forwarding node possesses the requested data item cached, and the node can directly respond to the requester with the item cached. However, if data corresponding to the interest packet has not yet been cached, the NDN Forwarder must forward the request to the corresponding content producer.

Layered Service-Centric Networking (L-SCN) introduces a domain-based NDN network split [4]. L-SCN describes two different communication layers. L-SCN distinguishes between communication in an *intra-domain* layer, which describes the communication among nodes belonging to the same domain, as well as communication over an unspecified *inter-domain* layer, referring to the communication among nodes belonging to different domains [4].

B. Distributed Hash Tables

P2P systems can be described as a crucial counter suggestion to traditional client-server systems. A Distributed Hash Table (DHT) overlay consists of a set of peers (*i.e.*, nodes), while each peer features a unique identifier (*i.e.*, an IP address) that belongs to a certain identifier space [3]. To enable communication among peers, connections are set up among pairs of participating peers. DHT divides the identifier space into a series of non-overlapping identifier ranges assigned to participating peers. All objects in the network have an identifier (*i.e.*, a key), which follows the same identifier space as the peers. Objects can be assigned to be stored on the peer, which is responsible for the corresponding identifier range. DHTs are also named-based; if some peer queries an object from the DHT, a routing function ensures to route the requests towards the node responsible for the identifier range to which

the object belongs. Depending on the routing algorithm in place and the shape of the network *wrt.* established links among the peers, the request possibly traverses a series of nodes until the serving peer is reached.

III. ARCHITECTURE

The approach had been specified and prototyped.

A. Specification

This section introduces the architecture proposed and implemented in this work. Inspired by L-SCN [4], this project uses a layered architecture, *i.e.*, an intra- and inter-domain communication. On the intra-domain level, we define several autonomous zones for mobile networks, which operate NDN. Each zone follows the typical hierarchical structure of a 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Long Term Evolution (LTE) operator, where only the hierarchically superior nodes are responsible for caching data within the zone. To enable communication at the inter-domain level, each zone elects one supernode at the highest level *wrt.* the LTE hierarchy [10]. Typically, a Service/Package Gateway (SPGW), which terminates the Radio Access Network (RAN), becomes the supernode. The operator can configure an arbitrary number of supernodes (S/PGWs), effectively creating subdomains in its network. Therefore, our solution scales with the size of the network operator. Zone supernodes are connected to the Internet and are involved in a DHT (*i.e.*, Chord DHT [11] is used), which is spanned among all the domains. Suppose, for example, some mobile node in a last-mile zone requests a specific data item, which is not (yet) cached in the local zone. In that case, its NDN interest will be forwarded into the direction of the zone's supernode, while the supernode translates the interest into a data object retrieval on the DHT.

Using NDN within last-mile zones is expected to enable in-network caching of data frequently requested by users' mobile devices. At the same time, deploying a DHT on the inter-domain level allows for a well-structured data storage and delivery among foreign domains. Since DHT operates over the classical IP-based Internet, an already established infrastructure is used for inter-domain communication. Hence, a global-scale NDN network is not required.

An exemplary topology shown in Fig. 1 consists of three NDN last-mile mobile networks (*resp.*, zones), with three data-consuming mobile nodes associated with each zone. Next to mobile nodes, each network features an intermediate node responsible for caching and a zone supernode, which is part of the DHT object-store. Communication technology-wise, all nodes involved communicate over the NDN protocol exclusively, except the supernodes, which are also part of an IP-based network to enable inter-domain data delivery using the DHT overlay.

B. Implementation

All simulations configured and carried out, involving NDN networks, are based on ndnSIM 2.7 [9], an open-source, NS-3 based NDN simulator module. Thereby, all nodes in the

Fig. 1. Joint NDN and Chord Architecture

simulator are equipped with the basic NDN data structures and their corresponding functionalities, *i.e.*, Content Store (CS), Pending Interest Table (PIT), as well as Forwarding Information Base (FIB), which are critical to NDN.

NdnSIM allows users to specify the forwarding strategy to be used when intermediate nodes have to forward Interest packets towards the upstream. The Best Route strategy ensures that Interest packets are forwarded to the (single) matching upstream node with the lowest routing cost. The Multicast strategy enforces Interests to be broadcast to all upstream nodes, which are recorded for the FIB entry matching with the Interest prefix. For the Best Route strategy to function correctly, complete FIBs have to be populated among all nodes. However, incomplete FIBs can lead to discarded content. The automatic population of integral routing tables can be achieved by an NS-3 routing helper [9]. Compared to Best Route, the Multicast strategy is less critical in FIB completeness. Furthermore, it is possible to configure NDN nodes to broadcast (*resp.*, flood) interest packets towards all upstream neighbors.

Chord DHT [11] is not part of the standard set of NS-3 modules. However, a publicly available Chord simulation module is available for NS-3 [5]. In this implementation, Chord protocol messages (*e.g.*, object lookups) are exchanged over the User Datagram Protocol (UDP) protocol, while for transferring data objects, Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) is used.

A crucial element for realizing the layered architecture is the bridging of ICN with DHT technologies to enable data exchange between the intra- and the inter-domain communication layer. Chord DHT Producer is based on the default ndnSIM application Producer [9], which processes new incoming NDN interest packets by responding with a data packet holding virtual payload. Chord DHT Producer translates an NDN interest into a DHT retrieval and eventually responds with data towards the downstream: If the incoming interest was previously requested from the DHT (*i.e.*, resides in pending DHT retrievals), the method immediately returns to prevent

the Chord overlay from unnecessarily overload caused by identical retrievals from the same supernode. If the DHT has not yet been queried for the data object, the new interest object has to be retrieved from the DHT. First, the object is inserted into the list of pending DHT retrievals. To retrieve the corresponding data object, the Chord DHT Producer extracts the query from the NDN interest and hashes it using Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA)-1. The resulting hash is used as the key parameter to invoke the retrieval routine on the associated Chord application, to which the Chord DHT Producer is assigned. The Chord DHT layer handles the lookup and data transmission at this stage. If the Chord layer calls back the data object retrieval as successful, a successful retrieval method gets invoked while the hashed key is passed as one of the parameters. The next task is for the Chord DHT Producer to determine to which interest object the retrieved object belongs. This is implemented in a method finding a corresponding pending DHT retrieval, which iterates through all pending DHT retrievals, where the SHA-1 hash identifies every interest object. If the key and the digest match, the current interest must be the one of which its data object was retrieved successfully from the Chord DHT. Finally, the method responding with data is invoked, which causes the supernode to respond with an NDN data packet to the downstream nodes.

IV. EVALUATION STRATEGY

To represent the LTE-EPC last-mile simulation, this work defines a custom last-mile network design, which mimics LTE. This custom setup is based on NS-3 Point-To-Point Channels [2] which allow for connecting nodes. The LTE network consists of SPGW, RAN, and User Equipment (UE) entities. A supernode on an SPGW element is connected to the RAN element with a 4 Mbps link, which fixes the RAN capacity at 4 Mbps. This roughly equals the capacity of the Single-Input/Single-Output (SISO) 1.4 MHz LTE system. The round-trip delay (15 ms) was configured on links between the RAN element and UEs. This reflects a typical round trip delay value displayed in a UE-SPGW communication in an LTE system.

The connected Watts-Strogatz Random Graph generation function was used to generate small-world graphs that determine the topology of simulated inter-domain transit networks [6]. The Watts-Strogatz small-world network is generated according to the network size, connectivity with nearest neighbors, and a rewiring probability. The rewiring probability used with the Watts-Strogatz graph generation algorithm was $p = 0.7$, while each vertex in the initial lattice was connected to $k = 3$ nearest neighbours. The data rate is set to 100 Mbps, and the propagation delay to 10 ms to simulate high-performance backbone links. We parameterize the total number n of mobile consumer nodes (UEs) and N , the total size of the transit network. Increasing n , directly influences the total interest packet load to be processed by the network. Varying N is expected to have an influence on the performance of inter-domain level communication.

Now, we describe a plainly NDN-based architecture, developed as a reference to compare our proposed layered NDN & Chord architecture. Topology-wise, the plain NDN architecture is identical to the Chord DHT network, as it defines several last-mile zones with a fixed number of mobile nodes, an intermediate caching node, and a zone supernode each. As described in the previous section, the inter-domain level communication among supernodes is transported over a small-world transit network. Technology-wise, however, this plain NDN architecture does not define an IP-based inter-domain communication layer; instead, NDN is the only primary communication technology that allows for simulating scenarios in which NDN is deployed globally.

To simulate data object popularity according to Zipf's law, the Zipf-Mandelbrot Consumer application is installed on all data-consuming mobile nodes. The Zipf-Mandelbrot Consumer is part of the ndnSIM reference applications and implements the Zipf-Mandelbrot distribution, a generalization of the essential mathematical representation of Zipf's law [8]. The Zipf-Mandelbrot Consumer application ensures to send out interests for low sequence numbers (*i.e.*, popular items) more frequently than for high sequence numbers (*i.e.*, unwanted items).

A set of fixed simulation parameters (*cf.* Table I) was defined to allow for fair comparisons of different simulation scenarios.

TABLE I
CONSTANT SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
No. of last-mile zones, supernodes	5
No. of individual data items per zone	100
Interest packet transmission frequency	10 packets per s
Zipf-Mandelbrot function parameters	$s = 1.2, q = 0.7$
Max. Content Store size	10 packets
Content Store replacement policy	Least Recently Used
Payload size	1500 B
Simulation runtime	10 min

V. RESULTS

The focus here is on the most critical metrics for the consumer (*i.e.*, retrieval time). As expected, in comparison to plain NDN with *Best Route* forwarding, NDN & Chord performs slower due to overhead generated by bridging between NDN and Chord (*cf.* Fig. 2). Note that the bars indicate the minimum and max values, while the line informs about the average delay. At the same time, various max. retrieval delay outliers indicate the inferiority of Chord routing compared to *Best Route* in plain NDN. This can be attributed to the fact that even if Chord guarantees low-complexity routing on the overlay, one hop from one Node to another might correspond to underlay traffic, which has to traverse multiple physical nodes, causing the increased delay.

Introducing interest *Flooding* in plain NDN has highly detrimental impacts on the Quality of Experience (QoE) (*cf.* Fig. 3). Compared to the *Best Route* scenarios, with *Flooding* forwarding deployed on all nodes, each interest packet is multiplied according to the number of the nodes' upstream

Fig. 2. NDN & Chord vs. Plain NDN with *Best Route Forwarding* ($N = 8$, $n = 200$)

Fig. 3. NDN & Chord vs. Plain NDN with *Flooding Forwarding* ($N = 8$, $n = 200$)

neighbors, which causes a severe amplification of NDN traffic; This effect is intensified. The more nodes lie between consumer and producer nodes; the more links are attached to intermediate routing nodes. Amplified NDN traffic caused by interest flooding severely strains the transit network, such that in some cases, data responses take extensive delays to arrive at consumer nodes.

Furthermore, we have noticed that NDN & Chord load the transit network significantly lower than the plain NDN with *Flooding*, and more than plain NDN with *Best Route*. Finally, the load on the producer increases with NDN & Chord compared to the other strategies, while the producer has to

respond to DHT queries directly. In plain NDN, caching in the transit network significantly reduces the load on content producers.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The contributions of this work are threefold. First, a layered network architecture for content distribution was designed, which combines ICN and DHT technologies. Secondly, the proposed NDN & DHT architecture was specified, implemented, and verified in terms of an NS-3 simulation by incorporating the state-of-the-art simulator modules, *i.e.*, ndnSIM and NS-3 Chord, to model the ICN and DHT communication layers. Thirdly, the suggested NDN & DHT architecture was evaluated and compared with the plain NDN reference by conducting different simulation experiments. In summary, the newly introduced NDN & DHT architecture has proven itself a well-performing option when it comes to interconnecting several independent NDN domains.

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